

A PROGRAM DESIGN FOR CONCURRENT ENGINEERING EDUCATION

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Abstract

This paper presents a challenge to engineering schools across America. Faculty and deans need to change curricula at both the undergraduate and graduate levels to prepare engineering graduates with the skills, knowledge and abilities to practice concurrent engineering. This paper points out the skills engineers need to have, what they need to know, and the needed competencies to work in a concurrent engineering environment. It discusses changes that can be made to engineering programs and recommends a curriculum for a graduate degree in manufacturing engineering that will provide graduates with requisite attributes. This curriculum is modelled after the American Association of Collegiate Schools of Business (AACSB) recommended structure for MBA programs.

Introduction

A new industrial revolution is underway in America. Instead of creating jobs as the earlier industrial revolution at the beginning of the 20th century, this revolution is reducing the number of positions and calling for a new breed of workers and managers. American industry is becoming lean and mean so that they can compete with the fierce competition from Pacific rim countries and Europe. And, they are also positioning to compete for a share of the declining defense budget. Surviving American companies are turning to a form of common sense engineering known as concurrent engineering.¹

The objectives of concurrent engineering as a practice are to improve operational effectiveness of and customer satisfaction with American made products, reduce the cost of ownership, minimize the potential difficulties confronted during the transition from design to production, and reduce cycle time.

1 Other names for concurrent engineering include simultaneous engineering and integrated product development. Some writers and practitioners also call it systems engineering. In this case it is said to be systems engineering as envisioned by early pioneers [2,3], not the sequential, serial systems engineering as practiced over the past two decades, or as currently taught in the colleges and universities of America. Lately there has even been a move in certain engineering schools to package concurrent engineering as design engineering.

Definitions and applications of concurrent engineering vary widely among the many writers on the subject (Table 1). Early researchers applied it only to manufacturing [4, 12]. Others have associated concurrent engineering with automation [1, 7, 11] and some have applied it to manufacturing and support [15]. Over the past 20 years American industry has not competed well in quality of products produced or supportability of products deployed. It is therefore understandable why there is a focus on these two areas. And with the advent and power of desk top computers, it is reasonable to see why automation has been tied in with concurrent engineering.

To compete, however, American industry needs to and is adopting a broader definition and application of

Table 1 - Definitions of Concurrent Engineering

- "A SYSTEMATIC APPROACH TO THE INTEGRATED, CONCURRENT DESIGN OF PRODUCTS AND THEIR RELATED PROCESSES, INCLUDING MANUFACTURING AND SUPPORT" IDA REPORT R-338, 1988
- "AS PRACTICED IN JAPAN, [CE] IS A GROUP PROCESS WHERE MEMBERS OF THE GROUP REPRESENT INTERESTS SPANNING THE LIFE CYCLE OF THE PRODUCT." TECHNOLOGY ASSESSMENT TEAM, 1989
- "THE SET OF METHODS, TECHNIQUES AND PRACTICES THAT:
 1. CAUSE SIGNIFICANT CONSIDERATION WITHIN THE DESIGN PHASES OF FACTORS FROM LATER IN THE LIFE CYCLE.
 2. PRODUCE, ALONG WITH THE PRODUCT DESIGN, THE DESIGN OF PROCESSES TO BE EMPLOYED LATER IN THE LIFE OF THE PRODUCT.
 3. FACILITATE THE REDUCTION OF THE TIME REQUIRED TO TRANSLATE THE DESIGN INTO DISTRIBUTED PRODUCTS.
 4. TO ENHANCE THE ABILITY OF PRODUCTS TO SATISFY USERS' EXPECTATIONS AND NEEDS." THE PYMATUNING GROUP, INC. 1989
- "THE SIMULTANEOUS AND INTEGRATED ENGINEERING OF ALL DESIGN, MANUFACTURING, AND SUPPORT ASPECTS OF A PRODUCT FROM CONCEPT THROUGH AVAILABILITY. IT IS A TEAMING CONCEPT." CE DIRECTORATE - US ARMY
- "THE APPLICATION OF SYSTEMS ENGINEERING PRINCIPLES AND OF MANAGEMENT APPROACHES. INTEGRATED ENGINEERING OF PRODUCTS AND THEIR ASSOCIATED PRODUCTION AND LOGISTICS PROCESSES WITH THE OBJECTIVE OF PROVIDING A PRODUCT AND PRODUCTION PROCESS THAT IS ROBUST DURING MANUFACTURING AND CUSTOMER USE. THE ENGINEERING PROCESS INTEGRATION BEGINS AT REQUIREMENTS DEFINITION AND CONTINUES THROUGH PRODUCTION OPERATIONS AND THE PRODUCT LIFE CYCLE." DIAZ, 1990
- "THE SYSTEMATIC APPROACH TO THE INTEGRATED, CONCURRENT DESIGN OF THE PRODUCT AND THEIR RELATED PROCESSES, INCLUDING MANUFACTURING AND SUPPORT. IT IS THE IMPLEMENTATION ARM OF THE TQM STRATEGY AND A MODERN TREATMENT OF SYSTEMS ENGINEERING THAT COMBINES QUALITY ENGINEERING METHODS IN A COMPUTER INTEGRATED ENVIRONMENT." UNKNOWN, 1991
- "AN INTERDISCIPLINARY APPROACH TO EVOLVE AND VERIFY AN INTEGRATED AND BALANCED SET OF LIFE-CYCLE PRODUCT AND PROCESS SOLUTIONS THAT SATISFY USER NEEDS." MIL-STD-499B (DRAFT), 1992

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concurrent engineering, especially those included in the military-industrial complex. The trend is to apply concurrent engineering to the total system design process and include development, manufacturing, test, deployment, operations, support, training, and disposal [8]. Although definitions of concurrent engineering vary, common elements include:

- (1) Simultaneous and integrated development of products and associated life-cycle processes (Figure 1). Customer needs are converted to a balanced set of products and processes through application of the systems engineering process to eight primary system life-cycle functions - development, manufacturing, verification, deployment, operations, support, training, and disposal.
- (2) Use of a systems engineering process (Figure 2). This process is applied recursively to each engineering effort during system development. The goal is to define customer requirements in technical terms; to develop the functional architecture that defines tasks that the system components must accomplish; and to describe the physical architecture of the system that satisfies customer requirements. Each definition is to the level of detail appropriate to the phase of system development; e.g., a conceptual system description from concept exploration and detailed configuration item descriptions from engineering and manufacturing development.
- (3) Employment of multi-disciplinary teams.

As industry turns to concurrent engineering to become competitive, corporate leaders are finding that there is a shortage of engineers and managers that are able to or desire to work in a multi-disciplinary team environment. They are also finding that there is a lack of understanding on how to design, develop, produce and deploy a competitive product using concurrent engineering principles.

Caution First let me caution the few who would desire to launch a new academic degree program in concurrent engineering. Don't! America does not need concurrent engineers. It needs engineers who can apply concurrent engineering principles in a multi-disciplinary team environment. There are already too many specialty engineering degree programs. Another specialty or discipline is not needed. All engineers should have knowledge of the concepts and principles presented in this paper.

The Need

What is needed are engineers with a balanced knowledge of technology and management. They need to have the ability to accomplish their specialty while working on a team with engineers and non-engineers that have different responsibilities for the product. A team normally consists of a core of traditional design disciplines such as mechanical, electrical, chemical, aeronautical, aerospace, material, systems, industrial, manufacturing logistics, and software engineers. This core team is supplemented by safety, security, and manufacturing specialists; and by marketing, finance, and contracting personnel as needed. This mixture of disciplines creates the need for communication, interpersonal relations, negotiation, and conflict resolution skills.

These skills are not typically found in today's engineering school graduates. Neither does one find engineers with the ability to accomplish the requirements analysis, functional analysis, synthesis, or trade studies, assessments, and controls of the systems engineering process (Figure 2) to derive a balanced set of products and processes for a system. Graduates generally do not even have an appreciation for what a system is. And, most

Figure 1 - Framework for Concurrent Engineering

Figure 2 - The Systems Engineering Process

graduates do not understand the economic or environmental implications of their design decisions or how producibility, supportability, testability, deployability, or disposability needs impact a design.

The Solution

Engineering undergraduate programs need to be rethought. Programs can continue to center on a discipline but they should also emphasize such areas as teamwork, leadership, change management, and systems theory. These areas can be easily incorporated into current undergraduate programs with individual or individual discipline team projects replaced by creative multi-discipline team projects. The dynamics of change can be introduced through such projects along with the requirement to take a holistic systems viewpoint of a project rather than focusing only on a small segment or specialty. Elective courses should come from such areas as communication arts and management.

Graduate engineering programs should be structured more like a MBA program than the current approach which is designed to give depth in an engineering specialty or discipline. MBA programs structured under AACSB guidelines 2 for accreditation require that entering students have at least 30 undergraduate semester

hours or over 18 graduate semester hours in designated common body of knowledge areas. In the MBA program a core of courses (15 to 21 semester hours) across all business disciplines is required to be taken to provide a breadth of knowledge. Students are provided the opportunity to specialize in a discipline for up to 15 semester hours. Additionally, most MBA programs have a capstone seminar that provides hands-on opportunities to work with other disciplines to start up and operate a manufacturing or service firm in a competitive simulation against other student run companies. Also, most quality MBA programs schedule colloquia utilizing business leaders to address issues germane to the environment students will face upon graduation. Many MBA students are exposed to business and manufacturing sites through class or project visitations, and/or are required to accomplish a team project or cooperative work effort. This AACSB approach provides the opportunity for a graduate student to experience the needs of other facets of a business in which he or she will be working.

Should not engineering students that will work in tomorrow's corporations have the same breadth and depth of experience as today's MBA student? I believe so.

A balanced graduate engineering program is necessary for the 21st century. Engineering school faculty and deans should consider redesigning their programs to be compatible with the concurrent engineering environment in which graduates of their programs will be required to work. Tomorrow's (and in reality yesterday's) engineering graduates must possess the following attributes [9]:

2 As the dean of two business schools for over seven years during the 1980s, and having started and administered a MBA program, I have working knowledge of the AACSB accrediting process and of MBA programs of business schools across America.

Skills:

- (1) Requirements and Functional Analysis - The ability to define customer problems and establish criteria that bounds potential solutions and defines solution success.
- (2) Synthesizing - The ability to generate alternatives, evaluate them against established criteria, select the best solution, and verify that the solution satisfies customer requirements.
- (3) Economic Analyses - The ability to accomplish cost-benefit trade studies and effectiveness assessments to understand the economic impact of the solution selected for implementation. These analyses are also helpful in the selection of requirements and criteria, and in the selection of the best alternative.
- (4) Communications - The ability to communicate ideas with other team members during problem solving efforts, to gain resource support, and to sell the selected solution to decision makers and customers.
- (5) Leadership - The ability to be a leader and follower in team endeavors and to be a change agent.

Competencies:

- (1) Technical - To be able to apply the principles and theories of at least one engineering discipline/specialty during a team design/problem solving effort; to have a holistic systems viewpoint of design problems undertaken by a team; to be able to apply the systems engineering process to the design effort; to be able to accomplish trade-off studies of alternatives and during requirements

- and criteria selection; and to be able to conduct cost/effectiveness assessments of design solutions.
- (2) Management - To be able to set goals, establish strategies, organize and allocate resources, make decisions, and control the activities of a team effort; and to have the interpersonal skills to get things done by and with people.

Program of Study

I recommended the program of study below to the staff of the Stevens Institute of Technology at Hoboken, New Jersey, during a 1991 workshop [10]. The purpose of this workshop was to establish a concurrent engineering emphasis in their manufacturing oriented graduate engineering programs. This same program can be appropriately tailored by adding and subtracting courses in level 2 specialty areas and in level 3 management studies as reflected in Tables 2 and 3.

Table 2 - Proposed Graduate Manufacturing Engineering Program

60 Semester Hr Program	Managerial Courses	Technical Courses
Level 3	Management Studies (12 Semester Hours)	Systems Engineering Concepts and Technique Studies (12-18 Semester Hours)
Level 2	Disciplinary Studies (12 Semester Hours)	Specific System Studies (3-9 Semester Hours)
Level 1	Foundational Studies (15 Sem. Hrs)	

Table 3 - Recommended Courses for Graduate Manufacturing Engineering Program

<u>FOUNDATIONAL STUDIES</u>	<u>DISCIPLINARY STUDIES</u>	<u>SPECIFIC SYSTEM STUDIES</u>
<p>COMMON BODY OF KNOWLEDGE (9 SEM HRS)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SYSTEMS APPROACH/SYSTEMS SEMANTICS • ORGANIZATIONAL THEORY • ENGINEERING ECONOMICS <p>ELECTIVES (6 SEM HRS)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE • BAYESIAN DECISION THEORY • MULTI-ATTRIBUTE UTILITY THEORY • SYSTEM SIMULATION • QUEUEING THEORY • MULTI-LEVEL PROGRAMMING • MARKOV DECISION PROCESS • CONTROL THEORY 	<p>COMMON BODY OF KNOWLEDGE (6 SEM HRS)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • TECHNOLOGY MARKETING • HUMAN FACTORS <p>ELECTIVES (6 SEM HRS)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • BUSINESS CONTRACTS • PRICING, BUDGETING, AND CONTROL • COST ANALYSIS • LOGISTICS • PRODUCTION TECHNOLOGIES • QUALITY ASSURANCE 	<p>COMMON BODY OF KNOWLEDGE (3 SEM HRS)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SYSTEMS ACQUISITION <p>ELECTIVES (0-6 SEM HRS)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • COMMAND, CONTROL, COMMUNICATIONS • TELECOMMUNICATIONS • ELECTRO-OPTICAL • TRANSPORTATION • ENERGY • WATER RESOURCE • WASTE DISPOSAL/ENVIRONMENTAL • MUNICIPAL • COMPUTER EMBEDDED • INFORMATION
<u>MANAGEMENT STUDIES</u>	<u>SYSTEMS ENGINEERING CONCEPTS & TECHNIQUES STUDIES</u>	
<p>COMMON BODY OF KNOWLEDGE (6 SEM HRS)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PRODUCTION MANAGEMENT • MANAGING PROFESSIONALS <p>ELECTIVES (6 SEM HRS)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PROJECT MANAGEMENT • RESEARCH & DEVELOPMENT MANAGEMENT • CONFIGURATION MANAGEMENT • TEST AND EVALUATION MANAGEMENT • BUSINESS STRATEGY/POLICY • RISK MANAGEMENT 	<p>COMMON BODY OF KNOWLEDGE (12 SEM HRS)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SYSTEMS ENGINEERING PROCESS (SYSTEM REQUIREMENTS ANALYSIS, SYNTHESIS, PLANNING & CONTROL TOOLS) • SYSTEMS ENGINEERING TOOLS I (ISHIKAWA DIAGRAMS, TAGUCHI METHODS, QFD, DESIGN OF EXPERIMENTS, SPC) • SYSTEMS ENGINEERING TOOLS II (CAD, CAM, CASE, CAE, CIM, CALS) • APPLICATIONS PROJECT <p>ELECTIVES (0-6 SEM HRS)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DESIGN FOR QUALITY, MAINTAINABILITY, PRODUCTIBILITY, AND SUPPORTABILITY • SOFTWARE SYSTEMS ENGINEERING 	

The program recommended is modeled after a MBA program with both a common body of knowledge that all students should possess, and elective selections. The framework for the 60 semester hour program is provided in Table 2. This structure ensures that both technical and managerial competencies are developed through a balance of core and elective courses. In this structure, skill development comes through implementation of individual courses. Each course would require appropriate team design projects, oral and written reports, and group problem solving exercises. The students would be expected to complete the foundational studies at level 1 before progressing to specialty courses of level 2 and integrative courses of level 3. Specific courses associated with the areas of study in Table 2 are recommended in Table 3. Courses in Table 3 were selected to provide a balance of specialty vs general knowledge. The student would be expected to select broadening as well as subject depth electives.

As with MBA programs, students entering the manufacturing engineering program should be expected to have at least 30 semester hours of common body of knowledge courses from their undergraduate program or equivalent graduate courses. In the absence of these courses, all 60 semester hours would be required for a master of engineering degree. Upon completion of masters degree requirements, a PhD program could be offered by adding requirements for additional elective hours and a dissertation. The title of the degree would depend on the area of specialty taken by the student.

Summary

American industry is changing to a concurrent engineering environment. Multi-disciplinary teams are being used to accomplish the simultaneous design of a product and its related life-cycle processes utilizing a systems engineering methodology. The graduates of today's engineering schools are not equipped to work in such an environment. Changes to engineering school curricula is needed to properly supply industry with needed team workers equipped with the necessary skills and competencies. The curricula provided in this paper is that recommended for the design of a graduate program in manufacturing engineering. It can be easily tailored for graduate degrees in other disciplines so that tomorrow's engineering graduates can meet industry's needs. This will enable America to become a world class industrial nation for the 21st century. America's economic future may well depend on universities providing engineers capable of working in a concurrent engineering environment. This is the challenge provided to America's engineering schools.

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About the Author

Dr. Lake is professor of systems engineering at the Defense Systems Management College. He is currently the President of the National Council on Systems Engineering; Functional Director of the American Society for Engineering Management; and principle writer of the revised Department of Defense standard on systems engineering. He is a consultant and has written extensively on concurrent engineering, systems engineering, technology/engineering management, and project management engineering. He serves as an advisor to the Air Force Materiel Command on systems engineering and to the Army Materiel Command on concurrent engineering. Dr. Lake is an aerospace engineer with advanced degrees from the University of Michigan and the University of Oklahoma. He has been recognized by several Who's Who awards and is a Fellow of the American Society for Engineering Management.